

The mathematical constant e and limits of trigonometric functions

Publisher: SungKun Kim

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n \\ &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{(4m+1)\pi}{2}-} (1 + \cos\theta)^{\frac{1}{\cos\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{(4m-1)\pi}{2}+} (1 + \cos\theta)^{\frac{1}{\cos\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 2m\pi+} (1 + \sin\theta)^{\frac{1}{\sin\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow (2m-1)\pi-} (1 + \sin\theta)^{\frac{1}{\sin\theta}} \\ &= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \frac{(2m-1)\pi}{2}-} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\tan\theta}\right)^{\tan\theta} \\ &= e \end{aligned}$$

The natural constant e can be represented in terms of limits of trigonometric functions as follows.

m is a real integer.